

JOINT AND ASSEMBLE OF HUGE COMPOSITE TOP-HAT STIFFENED HULLS

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ABSTRACT

Composite top-hat stiffened panels are often used in pleasure craft hulls as well as to build naval and merchant ship structures. One of the challenges in designing these composite structures is the high-strength joints. The article aims at the design, manufacture and performance test of the joint of composite top-hat stiffened hulls. Firstly, a bolted joint scheme is proposed to be used in top-hat stiffened composite panels. Then, the manufacture method of the joint scheme is described and test coupons are fabricated. In the test experiment, the failure modes and joint performances are investigated, and several design parameters are discussed. Finally, a scale reduced model is manufactured and the assembled method is validated dated using the joint scheme.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites have gained substantial attention as structural engineering materials in shipbuilding due to their outstanding mechanical properties, such as high durability, thermal expansion, lack of magnetism, high load-bearing capability and relatively low density. Bolted joints are often used to assemble larger composite structures. Several studies [1-3] have been conducted on bolted joints, covering such topics as composite bolted joint failure modes, analytical methods and the geometrical parameter design of bolted joints. The joint configuration has obvious effect on the joint performance. In recent years, researchers have investigated various joint configurations. Turaga et al. [4] proposed a configuration with attachments that transferred the load to strengthen single-lap joints. Li et al. [5] studied various composite butt joint configurations with different attachments. Bella et al. [6] designed and improved composite T-joints for use in composite watertight bulkhead connections. Bai and Yang [7] developed several novel joint configurations for assembling all-composite space truss structures. Caccese et al. [8,9] developed and compared many novel joint concepts, including Bolted Close-Out, Co-cured Metallic Insert, Metallic Extension with Secondary Bond, and Integral Fit (Mechanical Locking). These investigations indicated that joint configuration affects the mechanical performance of structures, and that an outstanding joint configuration should fulfill the following criteria.

- Provide outstanding mechanical performance and structural integrity.
- Reduce the stress concentration attributable to the joint geometry and abrupt changes in material stiffness.
- Be simple to manufacture and maintain.
- Have a suitable geometrical outline without decreasing the functions of products.

The foam inserted top-hat stiffened plate is the most commonly used structural element in the construction of composite ships, and forms the deck, hull, side shell and bulkhead. We provide a bolted joint scheme and design method for a top-hat stiffened composite hull. In this investigation, we compare many joint configurations found in the literature, and create a bolted joint scheme suitable for a top-hat

stiffened hull. We also propose the manufacturing method for this joint configuration, and create a series of test specimens. We study experimentally the failure mode of these test specimens, and discuss suitable geometrical parameters for the joint scheme.

2 JOINT SCHEME DISCRPTION

The joint scheme is proposed for use in top-hat stiffened composite hulls, so we must consider the following aspects: a) whether the one-sided geometrical shape should be streamlined or smooth, b) how to make a smooth transition between a top-hat stiffened composite plate and the joint area, and c) whether the stiffness of the stiffened composite plate should match the stiffness of the metal components. We have consulted several studies, especially the scheme of Caccese [9]. Our scheme is shown in Fig. 1. The joint area consists of two top-hat stiffened plates, a top metal clamp plate and a bottom metal clamp plate. To keep the external surface streamlined, the top clamp is designed to sink into the stiffened plate. To decrease the stress concentration and stiffness mismatch between the metal clamp and the top-hat stiffened composite plates, the two metal clamps are designed to have different lengths. Two foam blocks are used to smooth the under-surface of the joint area. The thickness of the foam block is the same as that of the top metal clamp. In the manufacture process, the top metal clamp is laid onto the mould. Then, the top fiber layer, the foam block and the top-hat foam bars are laid on top. After these manufacturing preparations, the resin is impregnated by means of vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) technique and top-hat stiffened plates are manufactured.

Figure 1. The joint scheme of foam inserted top-hat stiffened composite plates

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND TEST

Nine groups of test specimens were manufactured according to the parameters listed in Table 1, with five specimens in each group. Composite top-hat hulls usually carry tensile and bending loads. However, we only consider bending loads, and intend to investigate the tensile performance in future work. To characterize the bending behavior of these test specimens, we built a three-point-bending test using the ASTM standard. The load equipment was a Kexin universal testing machine (WDW-100), which can collect load and multi-point displacement curves simultaneously. The loading crosshead speed was 2 mm/min during the loading process. Higher load-displacement curves were seen in these specimens with larger metal clamps due to increased stiffness in the joint area. To decrease this effect and for convenient comparison, we collected the equivalent bending moment-displacement curves of the joint area axis. In the following discussion, we use the bending moment-displacement curve of the joint area axis instead of the load-displacement curve of the middle point of the test specimen. Firstly, we designed two load cases: load applied from above and load applied from below. To decrease the effects of different sizes of bottom metal clamp, we designed a third load case: load applied from bottom without a bottom metal clamp. The comparison of the two cases with and without the bottom metal clamp would reveal the effect of the insert block on the joint performance. The span of the support point was 43 cm.

Figure 2: Test specimens prepared

Table 1: List of geometric parameters

Symbol	Variable description	Value
L_1	Length of top clamp, mm	154.0
L_x	Length of foam block, mm	0,30,60
L_2	Length of bottom clamp, mm	L_1+L_x
θ	Angle of top clamp, degrees	15,30,45
t_0	Thickness of stiffened plate, mm	14.0,
t_r	Thickness of special reinforced layer, mm	2.0
t_1	Thickness of top clamp, mm	5.0
t_2	Thickness of bottom clamp, mm	4.5
h_c	Highness of top-hat, mm	t_1+t_r
W	Width of test coupons, mm	78.0
D	Diameter of bolt, mm	6.0
E	End distance, mm	4D
B	Boundary distance, mm	4D
S_r	Row space, mm	4D
S_c	Column space, mm	5D

4 FAILURE MODELS

In the failure process of these test specimens, we observed seven modes, as summarized in Table 2. In testing these specimens, we studied the relationship between the geometric parameters, loading direction and failure mode, as shown in Table 3. The main failure modes in the Case 1, as shown in the table, are BUAA and BUOA. The BUAA mode represents bearing failure at the top acute angle of the borderline of the composite joint area, and the BUOA mode represents a bearing failure at the top acute angle of the borderline of the composite joint area, as shown in Table 2. Both failure modes occurred at the transition area between the metal clamp and the top-hat stiffened composite plates, where stress concentrated as a result of a stiffness mismatch between the top metal clamp and the composite plate. The angle (θ) of the top clamp had an apparent effect on the failure mode. BUAA occurred at low values of θ , such as 15 or 30 degrees, and BUOA occurred at 45 degrees. Therefore, we conclude that the failure mode is related to the angle θ , which affects the stiffness transition of the joint area. The bearing failure of the bolted hole (BBH) mode did not occur when both metal clamps were mounted, indicating that the top and bottom clamps improve the joint performance. When Case 1 load was applied, cracking occurred at the lower clamp borderline (CDB mode), and the Case 2 load caused a bearing failure at the bottom clamp borderline (BBB mode). The crack of insert foam (CIF) mode usually occurred when the insert form was large, and the crack at the clamp borderline (CCB) mode was generally accompanied by a large deformation of the test specimen. Comparisons of the failure modes with varying L_x are shown in Table 4. From the table, we can find that the length of the foam block had a noticeable effect on the failure mode. The increase in the length of the foam block caused the failure mode under the Case 1 load to change from BUAA alone to a combination of BUAA and CCB. The same increase under the Case 2 load caused a failure mode conversion from BBB and CCB to CDB and CCB. This indicates that larger foam blocks may increase the joint bending strength, because CDB disperses stress on an area, whereas BBB concentrates stress on the borderline.

Table 2: Failure modes of these test specimens

Table 3. Comparison of failure modes with varied θ

Load direction	$\theta = 15^\circ, L_x = 30\text{mm}$	$\theta = 30^\circ, L_x = 30\text{mm}$	$\theta = 45^\circ, L_x = 30\text{mm}$
From above (Case 1)	BUAA, CIF	BUAA, CDV	BUOA, CDV
From bellow (Case 2)	BBB	BBB, CCB	BBB, CCB
From bellow (Case 3) (without bottom clamp)	BBH	BBH	BBH

Table 4. Comparison of failure modes with varied L_x

Load direction	$\theta=30^\circ, L_x=0\text{mm}$	$\theta=30^\circ, L_x=30\text{mm}$	$\theta=30^\circ, L_x=60\text{mm}$
From above (Case 1)	BUAA	BUAA, CDV	BUAA, CDV
From bellow (Case 2)	BBB,CCB	BBB, CCB,	CDB, CCB
From bellow(Case 3) (without bottom clamp)	BBH,CCB	BBH	BBH,CCB

5 DESIGN PAPAMETERS AND ASSEMBLING

We compared the ultimate strength of specimens with various θ and L_x values listed in Table 5, and found that θ and L_x noticeably affected the strength of the joint, indicating that the scheme is effective. When the load was applied from above, the test specimens with sharper top clamp angles achieved a higher ultimate strength. The ultimate strength increased about 20% when L_x increased from 0 to 60 mm. When the load was applied from bellow, the ultimate strength increased threefold when L_x increased from 0 to 60 mm. The enhancement of strength can contribute to the bottom clamp plate, by giving which a varying length (L_1+L_x) that matches that of the foam block. In conclusion, the ultimate strength with the applied load from above was larger than the strength with the applied load from bellow when the length of the foam block was small, and vice versa. As such, we can design geometric parameters to improve the performance of the joints in this scheme.

Table 5: Ultimate strength comparison of specimens with varied θ and L_x (N.m)

Applied from above / Applied from bellow	$L_x=0$	$L_x=30\text{mm}$	$L_x=60\text{mm}$
$\theta=15^\circ$	572.11 / 307.27	596.04 / 672.33	668.67 / 754.90
$\theta=30^\circ$	527.67 / 255.15	551.12 / 630.02	623.71 / 723.81
$\theta=45^\circ$	620.35 / 243.86	552.52 / 622.10	605.02 / 701.53

Finally, two scale reduced models of top-hat stiffened sections are manufactured by VARI tooling. The dimension of the model is $2\text{m} \times 2\text{m} \times 1.5\text{m}$. Flexible tooling method is used to assemble the scale reduced model, shown as in Figure 3. The joint scheme is described as above. Thus, a scale reduced model of top-hat stiffened composite hull is manufactured with dimension $4\text{m} \times 2\text{m} \times 1.5\text{m}$, shown as in Figure 4. In the process, flexible tooling is used to control the deformation of these two mode sections, and the deformation is usually caused by curing distortion and non-symmetric structure.

Figure 3: Flexible tooling process

Figure 4: A 4m×2m×1.5m model manufactured

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose a joint scheme for foam inserted top-hat stiffened composite plates, and present the associated manufacturing method. Test specimens were manufactured and their mechanical performance studied. From these data, we draw several conclusions. First, we identified seven failure modes, and found that the design parameters and load direction affected the failure mode and failure mechanism. We present the relationship between the geometrical parameters and the mechanical performances. Finally, a scale reduced model of top-hat stiffened composite hull is manufactured with dimension 4m×2m×1.5m, which verified the joint scheme feasibility.

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